

Short Communication

Local planning scenario for shading from trees as an urban nature-based solution

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ABSTRACT

With more than 75% of the European Union's population living in urban areas covering 21.5% of the EU territory, the importance of climate-resilient cities, towns and suburbs has increased dramatically. However, the rising impact of human-induced land-use changes on ecosystem services (ES) poses a major challenge to the urban environment. This study focuses on scenario development for nature-based solutions (NbS) in a European town with its intense development area. The concept is exemplified in a town in Croatia, Grad Velika Gorica (GVG), that like many others cities undergoes urbanisation processes with limited resources. It serves as a showpiece for the influence of NbS, in particular street trees along various paths.

Using spatial analysis and modelling, the approach explores NbS for future urbanisation. The results, supported by quantitative analysis, show that 49% of cycle lanes and footpaths in GVG can be shaded by strategically planted street trees. The shading scenario analysis provides a nuanced perspective on the potential of NbS, offering insights into the key tasks for a climate-resilient city and opportunities towards equitable, green and healthy urban areas.

In the context of urbanisation processes and climate adaptation, the study is in line with the overarching objectives of the European Commission which emphasises the need for sustainable NbS alternatives to address environmental challenges. The findings contribute to the framework of informed decision-making towards urban climate resilience. It also supports the pursuit of a sustainable local governance for climate-adjusted environmental quality in urban planning. As towns and cities grapple with the imperative of balancing urban development with environmental protection, this research highlights the central role of NbS, particularly street trees, in shaping climate-resilient and more sustainable urban environments for human well-being in cities.

Introduction

With more than 75 % of the population in the European Union (EU) living in urban areas, the urbanisation process on this continent is extremely high. Cities and towns are vital human habitats, yet they are facing increasing challenges from human-induced changes, particularly land-use pressure with their causal side effects [7,27]. Densification, accompanied by a reduction in green spaces, poses risks to human well-being and ecosystems. Human habitats suffer from built-up areas expansions and over 80 % of species habitats are in poor condition [6]. For this reason, sustainable solutions are urgently needed [7]. Urban areas,

including parks, street trees and forests, are facing constant environmental pressures due to climate change and loss of biodiversity [7,23]. All these features are part of the green infrastructure that are vital in cities because they deliver a broad range of regulating and cultural ecosystem services (ES) [30]. ES, defined as “the benefits that humans obtain from ecosystems that are produced by interactions within the ecosystem. [...] [They] affect human well-being and all its components, including basic material needs such as food and shelter, individual health, security, good social relations, and freedom of choice and action” [20]. Therefore, the loss of ES is emerging as a major environmental challenge for the dense European urban landscape [11].

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A typology of urban green infrastructure and its derived ES help understand which benefits urban planning can generate when designing and planning new greening in cities [14]. Nature-based solutions (NbS) are recognised greening strategies to find answers to key tasks for climate adaptation including human health and well-being in urbanisation [1]. NbS involve planned natural areas that provide multiple ES, thereby enhancing urban sustainability. Essential for conservation and restoration, NbS provide alternatives to traditional infrastructure and play a vital role in urban climate change mitigation [11,18]. Spatial planning using an 'ecosystem approach' is crucial for the sustainable provision of ES, highlighting the urgent need for comprehensive solutions [13,15].

The objective of this research is to investigate the influence of street trees as NbS on shading in public spaces especially along footpaths and cycle lanes. This analysis is illustrated using a European town as a scenario test site representing a typical living space. Significant, as the population living in towns and suburbs accounted for 35.9 % of the EU population in 2021 [9]. Including heat-related environmental pressures is essential for further management and spatial planning. Testing an NbS-related scenario is undertaken for the study area of Grad Velika Gorica (GVG) in Croatia. The resulting evaluation provides evidence that will contribute to informed decision-making towards urban climate resilience. It supports sustainable urban planning and climate-adjusted environmental quality in the study area by combining high-resolution spatial data and expert knowledge from local planners.

Tackling relevant environmental pressures.

Heatwaves are a major threat in Central and Southern Europe, causing the highest numbers of deaths among weather-related disasters [8]. On the one hand, the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) is defining this problem by setting threshold values for heat days and related stress [1], and on the other hand, the compounding effects of climate change are raising the alarm. Prolonged exposure to heat, exacerbated by climate change, increases the risk of heat-related illnesses, especially for vulnerable populations [16]. The impact of rising temperatures can also affect energy demand and escalate the cost of cooling systems and critical infrastructure. Shading by trees also significantly influences the choice of route for cyclists [34], an ever-growing group of road and lane users. Another side issue would be the transportation systems facing disruptions characterised by speed restrictions, material degradation and delays. The urban heat island effect can be mitigated by locally well-adapted vegetation, through their regulating ES such as shading and cooling [15,22]. Addressing these human exposures to heat stress is of paramount importance, especially in Central and Southern Europe, where resilient urban development is on demand to reduce such negative environmental impacts. Natural land cover, such as urban trees can help to lower the temperature and form so called 'urban cool islands' within an urban area, especially when compared to impervious surfaces. They can help to mitigate the urban heat island effect through evapotranspiration and shading [16,21,28,31,33]. The shade provided by tree canopies is critical in reducing the absorption of sunlight by urban infrastructure elements [28].

Research in The Netherlands highlights the social cohesion derived from the quantity and quality of street greenery, highlighting the central role of green spaces in promoting community well-being [29]. Conversely, a lack of green space correlates with feelings of isolation and inadequate social support [17,32]. In line with these concepts, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11.7 aims to ensure universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible green and public spaces by 2030. The Nature Restoration Act, a cornerstone of the 2030 Biodiversity Strategy, reinforces Europe's commitment to sustainable nature restoration [6,10]. In conjunction with the European Green Deal, it aims to halt the net loss of urban green spaces and tree cover by 2030. The Act focuses on halting the net loss of urban green spaces and tree

cover by 2030 and advocates an increase in the total national urban green cover of 3 % by 2040 and 5 % by 2050 compared to 2021 levels. Member States must set a 'satisfactory level' of increased urban green cover after 2030, to be monitored every six years [1]. The legislation calls for a net increase in urban green areas and requires Member States to develop tailored national restoration plans that contribute to EU-wide nature recovery [7]. The legislation sets binding restoration targets for different habitats, aiming to restore at least 20 % of the EU's land and sea by 2030 and all ecosystems by 2050. Implementation is crucial for biodiversity and for achieving the 1.5° Celsius global warming target [7].

Shading scenario along roads and paths

Due to the cooling effect of vegetation, and trees in particular, a shading scenario was developed to analyse the shading capacity of street trees on roads and, in particular, on cycle lanes and footpaths. This analysis was carried out using ArcGIS Pro 3.1.2 mapping software.

What are the prerequisites for the scenario? The first steps in the implementation of street trees were the creation of green verges with space for trees along selected roads in the area of interest. For the selection of roads, all primary and secondary roads were chosen, as well as all major roads that branch off from them. Only those footpaths, roads and cycle lanes that were in densely populated residential areas, as well as footpaths, roads and lanes that lead through areas where a large part of the space is already taken up by trees, were omitted. Cycle lanes and footpaths that run alongside major roads were also omitted, as otherwise there would have been overlaps with the green verges next to the roads. The Croatian planners agreed on taking assumptions based on German authorities' definition as no such reference values have been established in Croatia up to now. Therefore the model takes into account that the green verges should be 4.5 m away from the roads. The 4.5 m is considered the minimum distance as a traffic-related measure to protect against accidents involving collisions with trees (reference value according to [25] [engl. Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology]). Fig. 1 illustrates the assumptions made for the shading scenario.

The trees, placed as points on the green verges, were placed at regular intervals of 10 m (reference value according to Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie, 2020 [engl. Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology]). Due to the prevalence of different tree species in different European areas, the dominant types must be considered. In this test site in Croatia it is the European beech, with a share of 37 % of the total wood stock (FSC). Therefore, the study assumed this tree species for crown diameter calculations. [26] reported a mean crown radius of 5.5 m and a mean crown area of 93.5 m² for the European beech. A crown diameter of 10 m was chosen based on the above-mentioned literature and a visual analysis of the mean crown diameter of other trees. Mature street trees were assumed for the scenario, considering a crown diameter of 10 m, although the tree growth rate could not be specified. Linear growth was not assumed due to the slower growth of older trees, which is influenced by factors such as site conditions and light levels [26]. Practical assumptions were made, such as the sun is at its zenith and casting shadows at a 90° angle, although it is recognised that the movement of the sun and variations in canopy density may affect actual shading.

A second dataset was created using only cycle lanes and footpaths to see how well the street trees could shade these paths. Shading is most beneficial here because the paths are used by pedestrians and cyclists who are exposed to extreme heat, at least throughout the summer months. For those paths, a width of 2 m was set [12]. This was then used to determine the intersections of the two datasets, representing the shaded path area.

It is important to understand that beyond their benefits urban trees have some disadvantages. For example, tree roots can crack pavements, causing damage to public property and tripping pedestrians, and pollen

Fig. 1. Graphic visualisation of a shading scenario.

from trees can cause allergies in some people. It has also been found that at one point a too dense tree cover can reduce thermal comfort by blocking the wind through a closed leaf surface [16]. However, heat waves in Croatia are a main environmental pressure, and shading by trees is considered a central benefit with utmost priority for human health and well-being. Another beneficial aspect is that street trees can also increase property values due to their improved aesthetics [24].

Grad Velika Gorica (GVG) as study area

The research is carried out in the town of Velika Gorica (Grad Velika Gorica – GVG), which is located only 16 km south of the Croatian capital Zagreb (Fig. 2). Velika Gorica is the largest town in Zagreb County, covering a total area of 328.7 km². GVG is considered a rather rural urban area with a densely populated centre. According to the 2021 census, the town had a population of 61,075 people, with the main urban settlement of GVG hosting 30,036 residents [4,5]. The region is rich in gravel deposits, forests and groundwater resources. The extraction of gravel has led to the creation of four so far unmanaged man-made lakes neighbouring the town to the east [2].

The study area is characterised by a mild temperature, humid climate with hot summers (Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service – DHMZ). Monthly rainfall ranges from 54 mm to 98 mm, while

temperatures vary from – 3 °C to 27 °C [3]. Although the DHMZ collects all climate data for Croatia, only a few are stored online, and municipalities have to pay for local data, which is difficult for a town size of GVG to do. So it is even more important to be aware of the residents’ needs. Many citizens report that summers are getting hotter and hotter compared to 20 years ago, with the highest temperature differences likely to be around 10° Celsius [19].

Local planning pays particular attention to the eastern outskirts of the GVG, i.e. from the city centre to the urban extension areas. Here, urban planning aims to focus on these areas primarily and improve connectivity, as the new development areas around the largest lake are expanding rapidly and this trend is expected to intensify in the near future. In particular, the integration of the lakes is to be improved.

For the urban planning authority in GVG, street trees have enormous NbS potential to act as a green corridor both for biodiversity and as a rather cool walking and cycling route from the city centre to the blue areas. It is unfortunate that the cooling effect of the lakes for the city centre does not materialise, because GVG lies in a rather westerly wind zone. Nonetheless, the lakes are recognised as highly valuable NbS potential in the future serving as recreational and cooling areas.

By 2030, urban planning envisages a mix of mainly intensive development and the realisation of some NbS, which seems plausible in view of current developments and demographic aspects. In contrast to

Fig. 2. Location of Croatia in Europe (a) and GVG within Croatia (b).

the recent population decline, local experts indicate an expected population growth and expansion of living space [4,5,19]. This demographic shift is driven by commuter flows and makes land-use decisions even more complex, as it is influenced by rising land prices of neighbouring Zagreb and the continuing Croatian trend towards home ownership [19].

On the other hand, this development does not go in line with the EC objectives like the newly implemented Nature Restoration Law, which aims for no net loss of urban green spaces and tree canopy cover by 2030. The extent of the required increase in green space is uncertain as individual country targets have yet to be set [7].

After 2030 to 2050, a shift towards environmental protection becomes more likely, in line with the conclusions of the expert interviews, as GVG seeks to set an example of best practice in NbS and climate change mitigation in Croatia. These developments indicate growing environmental consciousness and the urgent need to address the challenges of climate change. As a partner in the REGREEN project, concrete steps have been taken to improve the greening of the city. Private enterprises have shown increased interest in funding activities such as tree planting, while surveys have been conducted to enable community participation and meet the requirements of citizens. As a consequence, the community has been sensitised to support the acceptance of the implementation of new NbS and to involve a wider group of stakeholders and citizens in the planning and implementation of NbS. The City Council has introduced a novel regulation that mandates all upcoming developments, irrespective of ownership, to preserve 35 % of the site's natural area. These regulations demonstrate GVG's dedication to promoting sustainable urban development and NbS [19]. After 2030, policymakers may face greater pressure to adopt new climate change legislation. This could still result in an increase in built-up areas in the surrounding settlements, while the city centre, constrained by high population density, is likely to experience further densification with a shift towards more GI. Continual expansion of a new development zone to the east of the lake suggests sustained growth and connectivity. Further development will probably also lead to an increased demand for NbS around the lakes. Improving the public infrastructure connection to and around the lakes and increasing their attractiveness for leisure

activities is therefore beneficial.

Implementing the shading scenario

Knowledge of the current situation is a prerequisite for creating the local planning scenario. For the status quo, an important observation is the presence of some tree-lined cycle lanes and footpaths. They provide shade and comfort for pedestrians and cyclists. However, roads to the east, particularly those leading to the lakes, presently lack dedicated cycle lanes and footpaths, for which reason the roads are not tree-lined. This resulting inadequate infrastructure with its shade deficiency has a negative impact on the accessibility and connectivity of the lakes, which are important recreation areas for GVG residents. The analysis also highlights the positive impact of street trees in the city centre for their aesthetic ES, beyond their regulation ES as mitigating urban heat island effects and cooling surfaces.

Integrating the analysis of a shading scenario into urban planning towards climate-adapted NbS strategies provides a useful perspective on the potential of shading by street trees. The analysis has produced the following result shown in Fig. 3. This illustration shows the areas shaded by street trees along the considered paths, highlighted in red. The following results illustrate the effects and significance of shading by street trees for the urban environment.

In this analysis, the total area of tree canopy on the selected paths were 735,000 m². The overlap of trees with the selected paths, which cover an area of 53,000 m² (marked in yellow) was 25,700 m², which means that about 49 % of these paths could be shaded by trees. Given the prerequisites of the scenario, the shading effect on primary and secondary roads was limited. However, the proximity of cycle lanes and footpaths adjacent to the main roads provided a significant opportunity for these areas to benefit from tree shading, thereby addressing the critical need for new NbS as shaded spaces.

The realisation of such a scenario could present a number of challenges. One challenge in implementing street trees as NbS in general in urban areas like in GVG is securing funding. Acquiring land for NbS often involves purchasing from private individuals, which requires significant subsidies and initial implementation costs. In GVG for example,

Fig. 3. Shading of selected paths by trees.

one hindrance may be preserving agriculture [19]. Economic aspects are seen as a major hindrance. Most of the land is privately owned and is already designated for a specific purpose in the municipal plans. Some of this land is already designated as a city park near the lakes, not necessarily as agricultural land. The main obstacle is the pricing of the land, which needs to be assessed by a court expert, and land prices have risen considerably in recent years due to its proximity to the city and rapid urbanisation. Only a minor area is owned by the government, and here most of this publicly owned area is already planted or there are plans for planting. Funds for the planting and maintenance of trees can be included in the municipal budget, but there are no funds to justify the purchase of land and these amounts are too high for the municipal budget for which reason project partners need to be found.

Conclusion

The main objective of the presented approach is to foster the efforts of a sustainable local governance for climate-adjusted environmental quality in urban planning. The impact of built-up areas on the environment is significant, leading to a multitude of environmental pressures such as increased heat stress, reduced access to green spaces and decreased carbon storage. As shown above, introducing street trees can have mitigating effects by their extensive shading capacity. The study has not only laid a first theoretical foundation by developing a street tree scenario. Beyond it has provided valuable decision guidance by its spatial visualisation. The findings presented demonstrate GVG's commitment to applying best practice in NbS to mitigate climate change. As an important heat management measure, planting trees is considered one of the most recognised NbS practices to mitigate heat waves. A purely technical measure to mitigate heat stress may also be to apply a white layer on the grey paved and asphalted surfaces, which is being examined by the local council as well. The dynamics observed in GVG reflect conflicting trends of increasing urbanisation and development of paved areas against the simultaneous demand for more regulating ES, which are shaped by political decisions, demographic changes and a growing awareness of environmental pressures. This quantitative analysis lays the groundwork for potential qualitative investigations into NbS implementation in its spatial context. The results offer insights into key tasks for climate-resilient towns and cities and the need for more climate adaptation included in land management strategies. Decisions made today will have an impact for decades to come, influencing the resilience, liveability and sustainability of towns and cities like GVG in general. As towns and cities grapple with the imperative of balancing urban development with environmental protection, NbS, particularly street trees, offer a way to provide multiple benefits to residents and a strategy to improve urban sustainable development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nicola Weidmüller: Conceptualization, Investigation, Visualization, Writing, Software, Data curation. **Julius Matthias Knopp:** Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Josip Beber:** Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Gordana Mikulčić Krnjaja:** Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ellen Banzhaf:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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